

Atmospheric contribution to Newtonian noise for gravitational-wave detectors

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Abstract

Third-generation gravitational-wave detectors are expected to have a sensitivity and a frequency bandwidth significantly larger than their predecessors. As a consequence, the atmospheric turbulence contribution to Newtonian noise (NN) could become substantial. In this work we present results about the atmospheric NN obtained using realistic turbulence models. Moreover, we compare the computed NN spectral density with the Einstein Telescope sensitivity curve with the xylophone design. We find that the noise decreases exponentially for small values of the frequency and the detector's depth, while it shows a power-law behavior for sufficiently large values of these parameters. We also show that, when the detector is built on the earth's surface, NN is above the minimum sensitivity of the instrument. Despite the noise being attenuated when the detector is built underground, passive suppression may be insufficient in strong-wind situations.

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Introduction

The first detection of gravitational waves (GWs), generated by coalescing compact objects, performed in the past years [1–10] have ushered in a new era in fundamental physics and astrophysics. Neutron-star and black-hole binary coalescences improved our understanding of gravitational physics, provided a way to test Einstein's general relativity and gave birth to the new multi-messenger astrophysics era.

Current GW experiments (LIGO, Virgo and KAGRA) use extremely sensitive Michelson interferometers to measure the effect of GWs in a frequency band ranging from 10 Hz to 10 kHz. Despite their sensitivity, a further enhancement is needed to test the gravitational phenomena at a deeper level [11]. Third-generation GW detectors are expected to solve this problem, pushing the sensitivity curve an order of magnitude below their predecessors and extending the frequency range down to 1 Hz. However, such an improvement exposes the instruments to more noise, thus requiring better modeling of every possible noise source. In particular, the gravitational gradient noise, also known as Newtonian Noise (NN), is the most worrying in the low-frequency band, i.e. in the 1–10 Hz range.

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NN is the fluctuation of the gravitational acceleration felt by the detector test mass due to some density fluctuation in the nearby environment. It has two main contributions from seismic and atmospheric density perturbations. While detailed models have been proposed for the former (for a comprehensive review, see e.g. Ref. [12]), the latter still lacks a realistic description. Indeed, our current understanding of atmospheric NN relies on the works of Saulson [13]—for pressure-wave contribution—and of Creighton [14]—for temperature-fluctuation contribution. Estimations following from these models predicted noise curves below the sensitivity curve of second-generation GW detectors by several orders of magnitude in the frequency band 10-10⁴ Hz, resulting therefore in a lack of interest in the development of more realistic models.

However, the situation changes drastically due to the great improvements planned for the upcoming detectors. Indeed, the currently available NN estimates cannot be extended down to 1 Hz using only the existing models, that are based on the quasi-static approximation and the assumptions of homogeneity and isotropy, which are expected to fail below 10 Hz. Moreover, some third-generation GW detectors are planned to be built underground, but no dependence on the depth was taken into account in previous estimations. Although underground construction is expected to passively mitigate both the seismic [15] and the atmospheric NN, quantitative analysis in the latter case is still missing.

In this work, we present our results [16] on NN generated by wind-advected temperature fluctuations, obtained by improving previous models. In particular, we relax the homogeneity and isotropy assumptions along the vertical direction and take into account the finite lifetime of turbulent structures. In this scenario, we find that existing models are good enough to describe the case in which wind-advection dominates over vortex decay, but a power-law behavior arises whenever the latter dominates, which was completely overlooked in previous models. This result is fully expected given the multi-scale nature of turbulent phenomena, and it is only weakly dependent on the specific model. Moreover, we consider an underground-based GW detector geometry and we explicitly take into account the dependence of the spectra on the detector depth. We find that, for great depths and sufficiently small wind-speeds, the noise scales not exponentially, but as the inverse of the depth. This means that passive mitigation through underground construction may not be optimal to fully eliminate atmospheric NN contributions.

Atmospheric noise from temperature fluctuations

We consider air-density perturbations $\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}, t)$ caused by temperature fluctuations $\delta T(\mathbf{r}, t)$, which are expected to be the major sources of atmospheric NN. Indeed, their contribution is estimated to be several orders of magnitude greater than the one caused by pressure fluctuations, which are usually dispersed in the form of infrasound waves.

Atmospheric temperature fluctuations are produced by the convective motion of air, which mixes hot and cold pockets of air at all length scales. If the detector is placed at the position $\boldsymbol{\xi}$, the quantity

$$\delta\mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\xi}, t) = -G \int_{\Omega} d^3\mathbf{r} \frac{\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}, t)}{|\mathbf{r} - \boldsymbol{\xi}|^3} (\mathbf{r} - \boldsymbol{\xi}) \quad (1)$$

gives the gravitational-acceleration fluctuation produced by $\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}, t)$, where G and Ω are the gravitational constant and the volume of atmosphere surrounding the detector, respectively. Notice that, in the reference frame shown in Fig. 1, the detector is placed at a depth r_0 and $\boldsymbol{\xi} = (0, 0, r_0)$. The acceleration fluctuation given by (1) has to be projected along the detector arm axis to get the actual noise

felt by the detector. Indicating with \bar{T} and $\bar{\rho}$ the mean temperature and density of air, respectively, and using the ideal-gas law, we have $\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\delta T(\mathbf{r}, t)\bar{\rho}/\bar{T}$. Here, the time dependence of $\delta T(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is due to two different phenomena: the wind advection of the turbulent structures and the decay of turbulent vortexes.

A direct calculation of the integral (1) is unfeasible, as it requires precise knowledge of the density perturbation field at every time. We can, instead, characterize the NN statistically, using its power spectrum $S_a(\omega, \boldsymbol{\xi})$, given by

$$S_a(\omega, \boldsymbol{\xi}) = \alpha^2 \int_{\Omega} d^3\mathbf{r} G(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\xi}) \int_{\Omega} d^3\mathbf{r}' G(\mathbf{r}', \boldsymbol{\xi}) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt C(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', t) e^{i\omega t}, \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha = G\bar{\rho}/\bar{T}$ and $G(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\xi})$ is the spatial Green function, $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency and $C(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', t) = \langle \delta T(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', t) \delta T(0, 0) \rangle$ is the autocorrelation function of the temperature field at different points and at different times. Notice that Eq. (2) depends both on the geometry of the system and the dynamics of the turbulent field. In order to separate the two contributions, we proceed as follows.

First, we note that the problem is simpler when we consider the autocorrelation function in the wind reference frame, indicated by the subscript U and given by $C_U(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{U}t, t) = C(\mathbf{r}, t)$, where the symbol \mathbf{U} indicates the wind speed. Indeed, with this substitution, we can ignore the Doppler shift due to the transport of vortexes by the wind in the power spectra. We can now express the correlation function $C(\mathbf{r}, t)$ in terms of its Fourier transform, which, assuming in a first approximation turbulence as homogeneous and isotropic, reads

$$C_U(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{U}t, t) = \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^3} C_k(t) e^{-i\mathbf{k}\cdot[(\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}')-\mathbf{U}t]}. \quad (3)$$

Here, the symbol \mathbf{k} is the wavenumber and $k = |\mathbf{k}|$. Now, we see that the geometry, sketched in Fig. 1, and the dynamics of the turbulent field are completely decoupled. Indeed, the former is only contained in the Fourier transform of the Green function, and the latter is encoded in the form of C_k .

The last important ingredient is the explicit form of the correlation function. In Ref. [16], we assume that time and spatial correlations can be expressed in factorized form

$$C_k(t) = F(k) \hat{h}(t/\tau_k), \quad (4)$$

where τ_k , called the eddy turnover time, accounts for the decay time of turbulent structures at scale $\sim k^{-1}$, and \hat{h} is a smooth function with maximum at $t = 0$, normalized to 1, and which is assumed to decay sufficiently fast for $t \gg \tau_k$.

If the Reynolds number is sufficiently large (which is the case for atmospheric flows), the spatial part of the correlation function is going to obey $F(k) \sim k^{-11/3}$, which is the so-called Kolmogorov scaling [17]. Through the latter, we can infer the decay time of turbulent structures, which can be written in terms of the energy-loss rate per unit mass \mathcal{E} and the size of the turbulent structure as $\tau_k \sim \mathcal{E}^{-1/3} k^{-2/3}$.

We can refine the description provided by Eq. (3) by taking into account the inhomogeneity of the turbulence in the vertical direction:

$$C_U(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{U}t, t) = \int \frac{d^2\mathbf{k}_{\perp}}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{dx_3}{x_3} F(x_3, \mathbf{k}_{\perp}) \hat{h}(t/\tau_k) e^{-i\mathbf{k}_{\perp}\cdot[(\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}')-\mathbf{U}t]}, \quad (5)$$

Figure 1: Representation of the geometry of the system used to compute the Fourier transform of the Green functions. The test mass is placed at the origin of the reference frame, at a depth r_0 relative to the earth's surface. We highlighted the Cartesian (x_1, x_2, x_3) and the cylindrical (x_\perp, x_3, ϕ) coordinate systems. The wind speed U_{x_3} , measured at a height x_3 , is taken to be parallel to the ground and to form an angle ψ with the detector arm, which is placed along the x_1 direction.

in which the wind speed is now a function of the height x_3 . For $x_3 \lesssim 100$ m, which is identified with the so-called surface layer [18], the wind profile is roughly logarithmic, $U \sim \log(x_3/z_0)$, where z_0 parameterizes the roughness of the surface. The values of the latter can span from $\sim 10^{-4}$ m for sand surfaces, to ~ 1 m for urban environments (see Ref. [19] for more typical values of z_0 of different terrain surfaces).

The function \hat{h} can be evaluated in the frequency domain by integrating Eq. (2) over time. The dependence on time is contained only in the function $\hat{h}(t/\tau_k)$. The integral is, thus, simply

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt \hat{h}(t/\tau_k) e^{i(\omega - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{U})t} \equiv h[\tau_k(\omega - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{U})], \quad (6)$$

being h the Fourier transform of \hat{h} . Knowing the explicit form of the time correlation \hat{h} would require a precise knowledge of the full non-linear structure of atmospheric turbulence, which is currently not fully understood. A reasonable choice that respects the criteria given under Eq. (4) (see Ref. [16] for further details) and provides an effective description of turbulent-structure decay is

$$h[\tau_k(\omega - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{U})] = e^{-\tau_k^2(\omega - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{U})^2}. \quad (7)$$

We verified that other choices of the correlation function, such as a top-hat function, do not produce significantly different results.

An interesting limit of Eq. (7) is $\tau_{\omega/U} \gg \max(r_0/U, 1/\omega)$, i.e. when the decay time of vortices of size U/ω is much greater than the typical wind-advection time. Indeed, under this approximation the function h reduces to a Dirac delta, meaning that the time correlations are only due to the wind advection and that we can neglect the decay of turbulent structures. This limit represents the frozen-turbulence approximation, which was already employed in the literature [14] to assess the magnitude of atmospheric NN in second-generation GWs detectors.

Figure 2: HI turbulence in the frozen approximation. **Left panel:** noise curves as a function of the frequency at fixed detector depth and varying the wind speed. **Right panel:** noise curves as a function of the detector depth at the fixed frequency $f = 2$ Hz for selected values of U . In both cases we set $\psi = 0$.

Results

In this section, we show our analytical and numerical results relative to the computation of the power spectral density as expressed in Eq. (2). In particular, we will focus on the three different models discussed in Ref. [16]: Homogeneous and isotropic (HI) turbulence in the frozen approximation, HI turbulence with finite correlation time and inhomogeneous turbulence. The extended set of the data presented here can be found online [20]. We compare our data with the xylophone-configuration Einstein-Telescope (ET-D) sensitivity curve as a reference for third-generation GW detectors. It is, however, expressed in terms of the strain power spectrum S_h , which is related to our gravitational-acceleration fluctuation S_a by the relation $S_h = 4S_a/(\omega^4 L_{\text{arm}}^2)$, where the factor 4 takes into account the number of test masses in the detector, while L_{arm} is the length of the interferometer arm.

HI turbulence in the frozen approximation—In the frozen approximation, the form of time correlations is particularly simple and it is given by a Dirac-delta function. This allows for analytical computation of the integral (2), whose solution can be expressed in terms of a combination of hypergeometric functions (see Appendix B of Ref. [16] for further details). The noise curves obtained under this approximation, as a function of the frequency or of the detector depth for selected values of the wind speed, are shown in the left panel of Fig. 2 in comparison with the ET-D sensitivity curve. We can see that the atmospheric contribution, in this limit, is exponentially suppressed for both large frequencies and great detector depths. Moreover, from the right panel of Fig. 2, we see that, because of the exponential behavior, the noise is negligible when the detector is placed at $r_0 \gtrsim 30$ m or when $f \gtrsim 5$ Hz. Moreover, we observe a monotonic growth of the noise with the wind speed U .

Although not explicitly shown in Fig. 2, we also found a power-law behavior at frequencies $f \ll 1$ Hz, which is predicted by our models (see Eqs. (19) and the discussion below in Ref. [16] for an explicit proof of this statement). As we shall see, the two behaviors (exponential suppression and power-law scaling at small frequencies) found in this simplified model are also common to the other two more realistic cases. This effect is associated with the interplay between wind advection and decay of turbulent structures. Finally, we stress that our results, obtained in a completely independent

Figure 3: HI turbulence with finite correlation time. **Left panel:** noise curves as a function of the frequencies for $r_0 = 5$ m for selected values of the wind speed U and of the energy-loss rate per unit mass \mathcal{E} . **Right panel:** noise curves as a function of the detector depth at the pivotal frequency $f = 2$ Hz for selected values of the wind speed U and of the energy-loss rate per unit mass \mathcal{E} . In both cases, we set $\psi = 0$.

way, are comparable to the ones already present in literature [14].

HI turbulence with finite correlation time—In order to go beyond the frozen-turbulence approximation and take into account vortex decay, we evaluated the integral (2) using Eq. (7). Differently from the previous model, however, the integral (2) cannot be solved analytically.

Additionally, the fact that the non-negligible contributions to the integral are concentrated in a very small portion of the domain makes the numerical integration particularly difficult and computationally convoluted. Thus, the computations were carried out using a VEGAS integrator [21], i.e. a Monte Carlo technique with importance sampling, together with the HYDRA framework [22], designed to perform data analysis and numerical computations on massively parallel platforms. Using this tool we have been able to compute the noise curves with a sub-percent precision in a reasonable amount of time.

Our results for the HI model with finite correlation time are shown in Fig. 3, in which we repeated the previous analysis for selected values of the wind speed. Moreover, we introduced the parameter \mathcal{E} , which sets the scale of the eddy turnover time τ_k . In this case, the results are similar to those shown in Fig. 2 for small frequencies and sufficiently large U . We can easily see that the noise is still suppressed for large values of f and r_0 , while it increases with the wind speed U and the energy-loss rate \mathcal{E} . Although not explicitly shown, we verified the presence of a power-law scaling for small frequencies.

Moreover, a new power-law scaling arises at large frequencies, great detector depths, or small wind speeds. This is due to the transition from a frozen regime, in which $\tau_{\omega/U} \gg \max(r_0/U, 1/\omega)$, to a vortex-decay-dominated regime, in which the decay time of turbulent structures is comparable or smaller than the wind advection timescale. This is also evident from the fact that the dependence on \mathcal{E} changes in the two regimes. Indeed, for small frequencies, large wind speed, and small detector depths, we see that the noise curves are weakly dependent on the energy loss rate. On the contrary, when f and r_0 are large enough and U sufficiently small, the noise curves do not depend on the wind speed anymore and their behavior is characterized by the parameter \mathcal{E} . This dependency on the parameters can be seen also in Fig. 4, where we show a contour plot of the NN curves as a function

Figure 4: HI turbulence with finite correlation time. Contour of the noise spectrum as a function of the frequency and of the energy loss rate at fixed $U = 10$ m/s (**left panel**) or of the wind speed (**right panel**) at fixed $\mathcal{E} = 0.1$ m²/s³. In both cases, we set the detector depth at $r_0 = 5$ m and the angle $\psi = 0$.

of the frequency and \mathcal{E} or U .

Another interesting and relevant new feature is the power-law scaling in r_0 for sufficiently large values of this parameter. Indeed, from the right panel of Fig. 3, we observe a $1/r_0$ behavior in the noise curves. This result is particularly relevant for underground detectors since it shows that passive mitigation could be insufficient to neglect the atmospheric contribution to NN. In Appendix F of Ref. [16], we show that this behavior is general and completely independent of the explicit form of the spatial and temporal correlation functions.

Inhomogeneous turbulence—We now want to relax the homogeneity and isotropy hypotheses and to study the inhomogeneous model. In this case, the correlation function is described by Eq. (5), and we once again consider h to behave as in Eq. (7). For the specific form of the function F in Eq. (5) utilized in the calculations, see [16]. Given the inhomogeneity of the turbulent structure, the values of the physical parameters entering Eq. (5) depend on a reference height, which we fix at $x_{3,\text{ref}} = 10$ m¹. Consequently, we will define a reference wind speed scale $U_{\text{ref}} \equiv U_{x_3=x_{3,\text{ref}}}$. Our results for the inhomogeneous model are shown in Fig. 5.

The general behavior is similar to the previous cases: the noise is still suppressed for large frequencies, for great detector depths, and small values of U_{ref} . Although not explicitly shown, the curves show a power-law scaling for small frequencies, as in the HI, frozen model. We also observe the transition to a different power-law regime for large values of r_0 and f or very small U_{ref} , similarly to the HI model with finite correlation time. This behavior indicates still the dominance of vortex decay over wind advection. Indeed, in this model, the high-frequency region is mostly determined by the turbulent structures produced near the ground (see Fig. 6), where the wind speed is small.

Moreover, we observe that the noise increases with z_0 for small frequencies, while it decreases with

¹Although this choice is arbitrary, it only affects the parameter u_* , and changing its value would not affect significantly the results presented in this manuscript.

Figure 5: Inhomogeneous model. **Top-left panel:** noise spectra as a function of the frequency, for selected values of the wind speed U and z_0 with $r_0 = 5$ m. **Top-right panel:** noise spectra as a function of the detector depth at the pivotal frequency $f = 2$ Hz and for selected values of the wind speed and of the roughness. **Bottom-left panel:** noise spectra as a function of the parameter z_0 at the pivotal frequency $f = 2$ Hz for selected values of r_0 and for $U_{\text{ref}} = 10$ m/s. **Bottom-right panel:** noise spectra as a function of the reference wind-speed U_{ref} at the pivotal frequency $f = 2$ Hz for selected values of r_0 and for $z_0 = 0.1$ m. For each case we set $\psi = 0$.

Figure 6: Inhomogeneous model. Noise spectra as a function of the frequency for selected values of the cutoff on the lower bound of the integral over x_3 in Eq. (5). The other parameters have been fixed at the values: $r_0 = 5$ m, $z_0 = 0.1$ m, $U_{\text{ref}} = 10$ m/s and $\psi = 0$.

Figure 7: Inhomogeneous model. **Left panel:** contour plot of the noise spectrum as a function of the frequency and of the roughness z_0 for $r_0 = 5$ m and $U_{\text{ref}} = 10$ m/s. **Right panel:** contour plot of the noise spectrum as a function of the frequency and of the reference wind speed U_{ref} for $r_0 = 5$ m and $z_0 = 0.1$ m. In both cases, we set $\psi = 0$.

it for larger values of f . This can be seen in the left panel of Fig. 7 and in Fig. 5. Indeed, as we showed in Ref. [16], the noise spectra are almost independent of z_0 for very small frequencies, while they behave as $z_0^{-3/2}$ for large f . This effect is similar to what happens in the previous case with the parameter \mathcal{E} , although here the behavior is more convoluted.

The last interesting point is the scaling with the detector depth, which is similar to the other models. Indeed, while for small frequencies the spectra decay exponentially with this parameter, for large f we find once again the $1/r_0$ scaling. We want to stress the fact that this result is completely general and independent of the considered turbulence model.

Finally, we observe that for fixed values of the parameters, i.e. $U = U_{\text{ref}}$ and r_0 , the noise curves for the inhomogeneous case are quite similar to those obtained under the HI hypothesis, at least in the region of interest for third-generation GW detectors. Indeed, all models produce results of comparable orders of magnitude. In the three cases, the curves are well above the sensitivity of the instrument for moderate wind-speed and when the detector is placed at surface level and building it underground mitigates the NN felt by the detector. However, for very strong wind (i.e. $U \sim 30$ m/s) the difference between the ET sensitivity and the noise curves is only a factor ~ 30 , as can be seen in Fig. 8.

Conclusions

In this work, we presented the main results stemming from the realistic atmospheric NN modeling developed in Ref. [16]. In this latter paper, we built models for the assessment of the atmospheric temperature-fluctuations contribution to NN in third-generation GW detectors, considering also the possibility to build the detector underground. We improved previous models by relaxing the HI hypothesis and the frozen turbulence approximation; specifically we parameterized the decay of turbulent structures by means of Gaussian time correlations and we considered the effect of inhomogeneities along the vertical direction. We computed the noise spectra in three key regimes. In the HI case

Figure 8: Inhomogeneous model. **Left panel:** noise curves as a function of the frequency for $r_0 = 50$ m and for selected values of U_{ref} . **Right panel:** noise curves as a function of the frequency for $U_{\text{ref}} = 30$ m/s and for selected values of r_0 . In both cases we set $z_0 = 0.1$ m and $\psi = 0$.

with a frozen turbulent field, we independently confirmed previously obtained results. We found an exponential suppression for large frequencies and great detector depth. Moving beyond the frozen approximation and considering Gaussian time correlations, we observed two typical behaviors in the noise spectra: one is an exponential suppression and the other is a power-law scaling. The former is dominant when the wind-advection time is smaller than the typical decay time of turbulent structures, while the latter becomes relevant when the vortex decay is not negligible anymore. In both cases, the NN spectra decay with the frequency and the detector depth, while they increase with the wind speed. Even when we consider the presence of inhomogeneities along the vertical direction, we see that the qualitative behavior is analogous to the one described above. Moreover, we found that, in the power-law regime, the noise spectra scale as $1/r_0$. While the scaling exponents for the wind speed, the energy-loss rate, and the roughness of the terrain are model dependent, the noise-decay exponent for the detector depth is completely general, and only depends on the chosen geometry. However, departures from the exponential scaling occur at large frequencies, i.e. when the noise is typically below the sensitivity curve. In the frequency range of interest—1–5 Hz—NN is always exponentially decreasing if the detector is placed on the surface. The spectra, in this regime, show a very weak dependence on the parameters of the models, apart from the wind speed and the detector depth.

We also found that, when the detector is placed near the earth’s surface, NN is well above the sensitivity curve for reasonable values of the parameters. Thus, atmospheric NN could represent an important noise source at relatively small frequencies, and should be taken into account. Moreover, we showed that passive mitigation does not work sufficiently well because of the slow $1/r_0$ scaling. Indeed, if for small or moderate wind speed the noise is well below the sensitivity curve, the difference between the noise and the sensitivity is only a factor ~ 30 when considering very strong wind speed (~ 30 m/s) and great detector depths (~ 200 m). Since our models should be considered as giving order-of-magnitude estimates, one should take into account a factor ~ 10 of inaccuracy anyway. Considering this and the fact that even the orography of the region near the detector might contribute to the noise, on-site measurements and numerical simulations are strongly recommended.

References

- [1] B. P. Abbott et al. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 116 (6) (2016), p. 061102.
- [2] F. Acernese et al. *Class. Quant. Grav.* 32 (2) (2015), p. 024001.
- [3] B. P. Abbott et al. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 116 (24) (2016), p. 241103.
- [4] B. P. Abbott et al. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 119 (16) (2017), p. 161101.
- [5] B. P. Abbott et al. *Astrophys. J. Lett.* 848 (2) (2017), p. L12.
- [6] B. P. Abbott et al. *Astrophys. J. Lett.* 848 (2) (2017), p. L13.
- [7] B. P. Abbott et al. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 116 (22) (2016). [Erratum: *Phys.Rev.Lett.* 121, 129902 (2018)], p. 221101.
- [8] B. P. Abbott et al. *Phys. Rev. D* 100 (10) (2019), p. 104036.
- [9] R. Abbott et al. *Phys. Rev. X* 11 (2021), p. 021053.
- [10] R. Abbott et al. *Astrophys. J. Lett.* 915 (1) (2021), p. L5.
- [11] M. Maggiore et al. *JCAP* 03 (2020), p. 050.
- [12] J. Harms. *Living Reviews in Relativity* 22 (1) (2019), p. 6.
- [13] P. R. Saulson. *Phys. Rev. D* 30 (1984), pp. 732–736.
- [14] T. Creighton. *Class. Quant. Grav.* 25 (2008), p. 125011.
- [15] F. Amann, F. Badaracco, R. DeSalvo, A. Paoli, L. Paoli, P. Ruggi, and S. Selleri (2022).
- [16] D. Brundu, M. Cadoni, M. Oi, P. Olla, and A. P. Sanna. *arXiv:2206.02610 [gr-qc]* (2022).
- [17] A. N. Kolmogorov. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A: Mathematical and Physical Sciences* 434 (1890) (1991), pp. 9–13.
- [18] R. B. Stull. Vol. 13. Springer Science & Business Media, 1988.
- [19] I. Troen and E. Lundtang Petersen. English. Risø National Laboratory, 1989.
- [20] <https://github.com/maurooi/AtmosphericNN>. 2022.
- [21] G. Peter Lepage. *Journal of Computational Physics* 27 (2) (1978), pp. 192–203.
- [22] A. A. Alves and M. D. Sokoloff. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 1085 (4) (2018), p. 042013.